

THE ROLE OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES IN ENSURING ECONOMIC SECURITY OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. *The article examines issues that allow one to gain knowledge on the basic provisions of the theory and practice of ensuring national security. It examines a set of problems of economic, information, energy and other types of security of the state and regions, their relationship with globalization processes. The theoretical and methodological foundations of the economic security system: elements, features, processes and structure are presented. The connection between the structural elements of economic security is demonstrated.*

Keywords: *economic security, national economy, theoretical and methodological foundations, socio-economic situation, training, education, upbringing.*

During the study of the discipline, it is possible to obtain and consolidate knowledge, acquire skills in working with government documents of ministries and departments in the part related to issues of ensuring economic security. During the training, it is necessary to remember that when implementing important socio-economic changes, conflicts escalate, often leading to protests, therefore, all the features, historical traditions, distribution of benefits, the influence of internal and external factors should be taken into account. In this regard, one should not rely only on administrative force, ignoring the laws of the market when implementing integrated prospective development.

The complex socio-economic situation in the country requires the construction of new promising areas related to the formation of qualities that a modern economy should have. The main trends are determined by the search for new forms, manifested in the integration of development resources. In the ongoing processes, the emphasis is on the quality of life and the associated flow of human capital. The main goal of national policy is to stimulate the efficient use of resources by building an institutional environment that ensures the implementation of the "social tone" of residents, and makes, in general, attractive to live and engage in entrepreneurship in the territories[2].

Studying the discipline allows mastering theoretical and methodological approaches based on the modern system of scientific views on national security in general, and on regional security in particular, from the standpoint of a systemic approach to substantiating ways of implementing balanced development of the territory during the implementation of cardinal socio-economic changes. The concept of "economic security" is relatively new in the lexicon of economic management.

This concept, well known in the practice of the management structures of Western countries, allows for a very broad interpretation. Economic security is a synthetic category of political economy and political science, closely related to the categories of economic independence and dependence, stability and vulnerability, economic pressure, blackmail, coercion and aggression, economic sovereignty, etc. In order to understand and comprehend the meaning of the category "economic security" it is necessary to characterize the term "security" and determine its essence.

The need for protection from undesirable external influences and radical internal changes, in other words, the need for security is a basic, fundamental need, both in the life of an individual, a family, and various associations of people, including society and the state. In the conditions of the formation of a market economy, the sphere of safe existence has narrowed so much that the constant and mass dissatisfaction of this need has a negative impact on the development and functioning of individual citizens, families, organizations, the state and society as a whole, aggravating the crisis state of all spheres of its life.

Security is defined by a number of authors as a state of protection of vital interests of the individual, society and the state from internal and external threats, and its implementation is ensured by the formation of a system of relations between subjects of public life (as well as relations "society-nature"), which are supported by a set of legal, force, administrative, technical and information measures. Currently, three basic levels of security are distinguished: individual, society and state, which in turn intersect with various functional areas of security.

The areas are represented by: external and internal security, state security, military and economic security, food and environmental security, transport and information security, and so on.

Economic security is one of the most priority functional areas of security. Today, the global scientific community has not developed a unified opinion on what the category of "economic security" includes. Some researchers tend to associate economic security with the security of the international economic system. They include in its problematic such issues as uneven economic development, rising debt, the spread of hunger, cyclical fluctuations, and other aspects of the general destabilization of the world economy[3].

Other experts prioritize the provision of favorable conditions for the most effective development of a specific national economy, including free access to foreign sources of raw materials and energy, stability of foreign investments, and guarantees of free exchange of goods and services. A number of authors consider economic security from the standpoint of the security of a region, industry, enterprise, or individual.

V. Pankov considers economic security from the standpoint of sustainability, and focuses on maintaining certain characteristics of the functioning of the economy in the face of unfavorable factors. In his opinion, economic security is "a state of the economy that is characterized by sustainability (immunity) to the impact of internal and external factors that disrupt the normal functioning of social reproduction, undermine the achieved standard of living of the population and thereby cause increased social tension in society, as well as a threat to the very existence of the state" [5].

E. Bukhvald, N. Glovatskaya and S. Lazurenko emphasize that economic security is traditionally considered as the most important qualitative characteristic of an economic system, determining its ability to maintain normal living conditions for the population, sustainable provision of resources for the development of the national economy, as well as the consistent implementation of national and state interests in the world. Academician L. Abalkin's point of view is to highlight the following as the most important structural elements of economic security: economic independence; stability and sustainability of the national economy; ability for self-development and progress. [7].

It is advisable to supplement such an element as "economic independence" by taking into account the factors of economic interdependence of all security entities, no matter what level they are at - national, regional or sectoral, at the level of an enterprise, community, individual, etc. The

concepts of "threat" and "security" are closely related to each other; it is impossible to conduct a full study of economic security without studying both economic and non-economic threats. A threat in general, and not just an economic one, is called such because it either creates the danger of destruction of an object or causes more or less significant damage to it. As for destruction, everything is clear here.

It can be understood, for example, as the deprivation of access to resources, leading to starvation, or the disorganization of monetary circulation, accompanied by the collapse of the country's economic system, or the loss of the government's ability to manage the economy.

Difficulties arise when an attempt is made to determine the level of damage that allows us to talk about a threat to economic security, but at which it does not come to destructive events.

Normally, economic threats are the reverse side of economic gain and a normal condition of activity in a competitive market environment.

Economic damage caused to an entity may be related to its inability to withstand competition and be the result of its internal factors, such as poor management. Damage may also be a consequence of the impact of external factors - both deliberate actions on the part of other states and spontaneous ones. In this case, the deliberate actions of the partner do not necessarily have to be aimed at causing damage, but may pursue its own internal goals. Natural events may be of a particular nature, relating to fluctuations in individual markets, or general, being associated with the destabilization of the world economic system as a whole[4].

A common view is that very few economic threats deserve to be linked to economic security. Most threats, its proponents argue, are related to ordinary, everyday economic activity and constitute its costs. What appears to be a threat in the short term, such as an oil embargo, may in the long term become an incentive for more rational energy policy and accelerated technological development. The damage may be in the form of lost income or the destruction of entire industries, and yet still be within the bounds of normal (and normally ruthless) competition.

An important aspect of the security problem lies in the country's relations with the institutionalized part of the international economic system. Thus, developing countries advocating for a new international economic order claim that they have been driven into a disadvantageous position in the modern system of interdependence. And since the existing international economic system does not provide them with the opportunity to get out of this unfavorable position for them, this system itself is considered by them as a threat to their economic security. Most researchers try to classify and generalize threats. All threats are divided into threats to international, national and regional economic security, as well as threats to the economic security of an enterprise and an individual.

There are two approaches to classifying threats: classification by threat source and by threat type. When classifying economic security threats "by source", they are divided into two large groups - threats of economic and political origin. The source of most environmental, criminal and other threats are imperfections of economic and political institutions or economic and political processes occurring in the international system (such as globalization, political integration, development of information technology, etc.). Using the example of classifying threats to national economic security, we will consider the classification of threats "by source"[6].

As a rule, sources of threats are classified by their nature (internal or external) or type (economic or political). There may be significantly more types of threats, for example, some authors separately identify innovative, investment, financial, scientific and technical,

demographic, environmental, food security threats, etc. The main subject of ensuring security is the state, which carries out functions in this area through legislative, executive and judicial authorities. The state, in accordance with current legislation, ensures the security of each citizen located outside its borders.

In addition, security subjects are citizens, public organizations and associations that have rights and obligations to ensure security in accordance with the law. According to the definition of the State Standard: a person or group of people who influence security. Security objects are a part of the material world allocated by the subject for the purpose of security management. The main security objects are: the individual - his rights and freedoms, society - its material and spiritual values, the state - its constitutional system, sovereignty and territorial integrity. Security objects also include enterprises, associations, institutions of the real or immaterial sphere of production[9].

In order to create and maintain the necessary level of security of security facilities, a system of legal norms regulating relations in the field of security is developed, the main areas of activity of state authorities and administration in this area are determined, security agencies and a mechanism for monitoring and overseeing their activities are formed or transformed.

In order to directly perform functions to ensure the security of the individual, society and the state, state security agencies are formed in the executive power system in accordance with the Law.

The subject of state activity in the field of economic security:

- identification and monitoring of factors that undermine the stability of the socio-economic system and the state in the short and long term;
- formation and implementation of economic policy and institutional reforms that eliminate or mitigate the harmful effects of these factors within the framework of a single economic reform program.

Economic security is a state of the economy that ensures a sufficient level of social, political, defense existence and progressive development of the security entity, the invulnerability and independence of its economic interests in relation to possible external and internal threats and impacts[8].

Based on this concept, we will define the structure of economic security. Economic security itself has a rather complex internal structure. Three of its most important elements can be distinguished:

- economic independence, which in the conditions of the modern world economy is by no means absolute. The international division of labor makes national economies interdependent on each other. In these conditions, economic independence means the possibility of state control over national resources.

Achieving a level of production efficiency and product quality that ensures:

- its competitiveness and allows equal participation in world trade, exchange of scientific and technical achievements;
- stability and sustainability of the national economy, implying the protection of property in all its forms, the creation of reliable conditions and guarantees for entrepreneurial activity, the fight against criminal structures in the economy, the prevention of serious gaps in the distribution of income that threaten to cause social upheavals, etc.

- the ability to self-development and progress, which is especially important in today's dynamically developing world. Creating a favorable climate for investment and innovation, constant modernization of production, raising the professional, educational and general cultural level of workers are becoming necessary and mandatory conditions for the sustainability and self-preservation of the national economy.

Thus, the structure of economic security is defined from the point of view of three levels of economic security: national, local (regional) and private (enterprises). National economic security can be represented in the form of eight closely related structural elements: demographic security, economic security, spiritual and moral security, information security, environmental security, political security, defense (military) security and social security.

The peculiarity of threats of a microeconomic nature is that they are associated with the activities of economic entities located in the region. Meso-level threats include the loss of the domestic market, reproductive independence, and the loss of the ability to provide food self-sufficiency at the regional level.

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